

**MOLECULAR STRUCTURE, NMR, HOMO-LUMO AND VIBRATIONAL ANALYSIS OF
GAMMA O- NITROBENZALDEHYDE OXIME BASED ON DENSITY FUNCTIONAL
THEORY CALCULATIONS**

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the experimental and theoretical spectra of O- Nitrobenzaldehyde oxime were studied. The FTIR and FT-Raman spectra of O- Nitrobenzaldehyde oxime have been recorded in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹ and 4000-50 cm⁻¹, respectively. The molecular structure, geometry optimization and harmonic vibrational frequencies have been investigated. The spectra were interpreted with the aid of normal coordinate analysis based on the density functional theory (DFT) using the standard B3LYP/6-31G* method and basis set combination and was scaled using multiple scale factors yield good agreement between observed and calculated frequencies. The results of the calculations are applied to simulate Infrared and Raman spectra of the title compound which showed reasonable agreement with the observed spectra. The substituent of nitro group which is electron withdrawing group in an aromatic ring system makes a remarkable effect on the geometric and spectroscopic properties of the title compound are also discussed. Quantum chemical parameters such as highest occupied molecular orbital energy (E_{HOMO}), the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital energy (E_{LUMO}), energy gap (ΔE), chemical potential (P_i), global hardness (η), and the softness (σ) were calculated. ¹H and ¹³C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) chemical shifts of the molecule were calculated by using gauge invariant atomic orbital (GIAO) method. In addition, molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) and Mulliken atomic charges were determined. Thermodynamic properties of the title compound have been calculated.

Key words: O- Nitrobenzaldehyde oxime, Vibrational frequencies, HOMO-LUMO, NMR.

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